

Activity: public outreach talk at Daejeon Science Highschool

Title: Astronomy, Solar System and Extrasolar Planets

Date: 08. November 2013

Place: Daejeon, Republic of Korea (South Korea)

Lecturer / speaker: T. C. Hinse





